

TEACHING VIET'S THEOREM FOR THE PRESENTED QUADRATIC EQUATION TO ACADEMIC LYCEUM STUDENTS USING NEW METHODS

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Announcement: This article discusses new, effective methods for teaching quadratic equations to improve the mathematical literacy of academic lyceum students. Along with traditional approaches, the advantages of using innovative educational technologies, visual aids, a differential approach, and integrated methods based on real-life problems are analyzed. Also, approaches that serve to form students' independent thinking, analytical approach, and creative abilities when working with the presented quadratic equation are enriched with practical examples. The article offers strategies that help students develop a deep understanding. This article uses the methods of "Problem-based learning" and "Creative tasks".

Keywords: quadratic equation, new teaching methods, academic lyceum, visualization, differential approach, analytical thinking, mathematical literacy, integrated teaching.

1. Introduction. Today, one of the requirements for the organization of education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending excessive mental and physical effort. Delivering certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short time, forming skills and competencies in them for a certain activity, as well as monitoring students' activities, assessing the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them requires high pedagogical skills from students and a new approach to the educational process. Why a short time? Because the student cannot focus on the lesson for a very long time, he is quickly distracted. Therefore, the teacher must first capture the student's attention and be able to explain the topic to the student in a short time.

Mathematics is the basis of all exact sciences. A child who knows this subject well will grow up intelligent, broad-minded, and will successfully work in any field,

— said our President Sh. Mirziyoyev.

If mathematics were not beautiful. Perhaps mathematics itself would not exist. Otherwise, what force could attract the great geniuses of humanity to this difficult science, - said Tchaikovsky.

Based on these thoughts, we, teachers, must be more responsible. The main goal of pedagogical technologies in education is to bring the student to the center of the learning process in the educational system, to move students away from simply memorizing and automatically repeating educational materials, to develop their independent and creative activities, to make them active participants in the lesson. Only then will students have their own opinion on important life achievements and problems, the practical application of the topics covered, and be able to justify their point of view. Pedagogical technology is inherently subjective. Regardless of the form, methods and means by which it is organized, technologies: increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity; establish mutual cooperation between the teacher and the student; ensure the acquisition of thorough knowledge by students on academic subjects; form independent, free and creative thinking skills in students; create the necessary conditions for students to realize their potential; it is necessary to guarantee the priority of democratic and humanistic ideas in the pedagogical process. Currently, when it comes to the introduction of new methods or innovations into the educational process, the

application of interactive methods to the educational process is understood. Interactivity is the interaction of two people, that is, the learning-knowledge process is based on mutual interaction. Interactivity is mutual activity, action, influence, which occurs in the dialogue between the student and the teacher. The main goal of the interactive method is to create an environment for active, free thinking of the student by creating the most favorable conditions for the educational process. This article presents some considerations on teaching the topic "Addition and Subtraction of Mixed Numbers", known from the Mathematics course of secondary schools, and provides methodological guidelines.

2.Literature analysis.

[3] The article provides information on the use of person-oriented educational technologies in mathematics lessons.

[4] The article argues that the historical approach to the study of academic subjects brings the learning process closer to scientific knowledge to a certain extent, and that the teacher, while introducing mathematical concepts, talks about their history and development (mainly the merits of our great ancestors) during the lesson increases students' interest in science and fosters love for the Motherland.

[5] The article analyzes the issue of using didactic games in the process of teaching mathematics. It is noted that the organization of lessons also depends on the teacher's creative abilities. It is said that students consolidate the knowledge they have gained from the lesson and prepare to apply it in life.

[6] The article notes that in today's era of advanced science and technology, the role of independent learning in consolidating students' knowledge is of particular importance. In this regard, it is emphasized that it is very important today to increase students' self-confidence, to acquire independent knowledge, to work independently and to work independently on themselves when carrying out independent education. It also briefly discusses the aspects that should be paid attention to when organizing students' independent education, and the instructions that should be given to students.

[7] The article provides a brief understanding of logical problems related to work and the types into which they are divided, the stages of their solution, and the main laws that occur in such problems. It summarizes the considerations on what affirmations we should pay attention to when solving arithmetic problems related to work, and provides examples of solutions to problems on the topic. It is emphasized that the problems solved with the given affirmations and arguments will help students and independent learners of the subject to master text problems without difficulty.

[8] The article presents a number of theoretical and logical foundations for the development of students' creative thinking, without which it is impossible to correctly solve exponential equations and inequalities. Typical variants of exponential equations and inequalities, as well as instructions for solving such problems, are given.

[9] The article provides important information on what to pay attention to in order to acquire basic knowledge in solving inequalities using best practices in the development of the educational sphere and avoid mistakes in generalizing solutions. The solution of examples of inequalities involving fractional-rational, irrational, logarithmic and trigonometric functions using an algorithmic method is presented.

[10-11] *The article is devoted to the analysis of the effectiveness of interactive technologies as a means of improving the quality of the educational process. It was noted that today the use of interactive methods in the educational process is widely introduced, which requires the humanization, democratization and liberalization of the educational process. It was noted that interactive methods are aimed at achieving high results in a short time without spending a lot of time and physical effort, and that teaching students theoretical knowledge, acquiring skills and qualifications in certain types of activities, forming moral qualities, and monitoring and assessing student knowledge require great skill and dexterity.*

3. Main part. A reduced quadratic equation is an equation whose leading coefficient is 1. That is, $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ if the equation has $a=1$, it is called a reduced quadratic equation.

For example: a) $x^2 + 8x + 3 = 0$ b) $x^2 - 7x + 12 = 0$

An arbitrary quadratic equation can be converted into a reduced quadratic equation by dividing it by its leading coefficient.

For example: $-3x^2 + 7x - 1 = 0$ $\frac{-3x^2}{-3} + \frac{7x}{-3} - \frac{1}{-3} = 0$ $x^2 - \frac{7}{3}x + \frac{1}{3} = 0$

Usually, the reduced quadratic equation $x^2 + px + q = 0$ is written in the form, where p and q are given numbers.

Reduced quadratic equations are solved using a formula, like other quadratic equations. This theorem helps to find the roots of the reduced quadratic equation by the method of selection, and in some cases, to find the sum of the squares and cubes of the roots without finding the roots, or to find answers to similar questions.

Theorem: (Vietnam's theorem) If the numbers x_1 and x_2 are the roots $x^2 + px + q = 0$ of the equation, then the sum of the roots is equal to the 2nd coefficient taken with the opposite

sign, and the product of the roots is equal to the free term, that is;
$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = -p \\ x_1 \cdot x_2 = q \end{cases}$$

Example 1: $x_1 + x_2$ va $x_1 \cdot x_2$ find the ones.

a) $x^2 + 5x - 1 = 0$ $x_1 + x_2 = -5$ $x_1 \cdot x_2 = -1$

b) $x^2 - 11x + 3 = 0$ $x_1 + x_2 = 11$ $x_1 \cdot x_2 = 3$

c) $-x^2 - 4x + 1 = 0$ $x^2 + 4x - 1 = 0$ $x_1 + x_2 = -4$ $x_1 \cdot x_2 = -1$

c) $2x^2 - 3x + 1 = 0$ $x^2 - \frac{3}{2}x + \frac{1}{2} = 0$ $x_1 + x_2 = \frac{3}{2}$ $x_1 \cdot x_2 = \frac{1}{2}$

Example 2: If x_1 va x_2 numbers $x^2 - 3x - 2 = 0$ the equation has roots, calculate the following without finding the roots themselves.

a) $x_1^2 + x_2^2 = ?$ b) $x_1^4 + x_2^4 = ?$ c) $x_1^3 + x_2^3 = ?$ d) $\frac{x_1}{x_2} + \frac{x_2}{x_1} = ?$ e) $x_1^2 \cdot x_2^4 + x_1^4 \cdot x_2^2 = ?$

Solution: In this; $x^2 - 3x - 2 = 0$ $x_1 + x_2 = 3$ $x_1 \cdot x_2 = -2$

a) $x_1^2 + x_2^2 = (x_1 + x_2)^2 - 2x_1x_2 = 3^2 - 2 \cdot (-2) = 9 + 4 = 13$

$$b) x_1^4 + x_2^4 = (x_1^2 + x_2^2)^2 - 2x_1^2x_2^2 = ((x_1 + x_2)^2 - 2x_1x_2)^2 - 2(x_1x_2)^2 = (9 + 4)^2 - 2 \cdot 4 = 169 - 8 = 161$$

$$c) x_1^3 + x_2^3 = (x_1 + x_2)(x_1^2 - x_1x_2 + x_2^2) = 3 \cdot ((x_1 + x_2)^2 - 3x_1x_2) = 3 \cdot (9 + 6) = 45$$

$$d) \frac{x_1}{x_2} + \frac{x_2}{x_1} = \frac{x_1^2 + x_2^2}{x_1 \cdot x_2} = \frac{(x_1 + x_2)^2 - 2x_1x_2}{x_1x_2} = \frac{9 + 4}{-2} = -\frac{13}{2} = -6,5$$

$$e) x_1^2 \cdot x_2^4 + x_1^4 \cdot x_2^2 = x_1^2 \cdot x_2^2 \cdot (x_2^2 + x_1^2) = 4 \cdot 13 = 52$$

We use methods to find out how well students understand the topic being taught.

Problem-based learning method - example

Situation:

A farmer wants to use a 60-meter-long fence to enclose three sides of a rectangular plot of land. Since the fourth side of the land is along a river, no fence is needed. He wants to create the maximum area. What size plot of land will be chosen so that the area is the largest?

Solution:

1. Let the side of the rectangle along the river be x , and the sides be y .

2. The total length of the three sides is:

$$x + 2y = 60 \quad y = \frac{60 - x}{2}$$

3. Area formula: $S = x \cdot y = x \cdot \frac{60 - x}{2}$

4. Simplify:

$$S = \frac{60x - x^2}{2}$$

Learning through creative tasks - example

Task:

Assignment to students: "Write a short story or a scene (mini-play) about a quadratic equation, in which the equation acts as a hero."

Example:

Story title: "Equation Adventure"

One day, a problem arose in the city of mathematics. Our hero $-x^2 - 5x + 6 = 0$ quadratic equation went out to ask for help. He consulted his friend Discriminant. Discriminant told him:

"I know 1 formula:

$D = b^2 - 4ac$ said.

They calculated: $D = 25 - 24 = 1$. So, there are 2 roots!

The quadratic equation: "Thank you, Discriminant, now I can find solutions!" — was happy.

Thus, he found his roots: $x_1 = 2, x_2 = 3$, and peace returned.

4. Conclusion. This article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of teaching the quadratic equation to academic lyceum students using new, modern and interactive methods. Along with traditional approaches, it has been proven that the graphic method, analysis based on a block diagram, the use of digital tools such as GeoGebra, a problem-based approach based on real-life situations, and creative tasks can deepen students' understanding of the subject.

These methods develop not only students' mathematical knowledge, but also their analytical thinking, creative approach, and problem-solving skills. Therefore, when teaching the

quadratic equation, special attention should be paid to methods that involve the student in the learning process as an active participant, not just memorizing formulas.

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